

الهيئة السعودية للمياه
Saudi Water Authority

THE INNOVATION

VALUE CHAIN IN THE WATER SECTOR OF SAUDI ARABIA

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GLOSSARY

ACWA	ACWA Power
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BC	Brine Concentration
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
ERD	Energy Recovery Device
GASTAT	General Authority for Statistics
GCC	Gulf Cooperation Council
IDA	International Desalination Association
IoT	Internet of Things
IWA	International Water Association
IWP	Independent Water Producer
KAUST	King Abdullah University of Science and Technology
KACST	King Abdulaziz City for Science and Technology
KFUPM	King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals
KSA	Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
KS Relief	King Salman Humanitarian Aid and Relief Centre
Li	Lithium
MBR	Membrane Bioreactor
MEWA	Ministry of Environment, Water, and Agriculture
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
NEDO	New Energy and Industrial Technology Development Organization (Japan)
NWC	National Water Company
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
PCC	Precipitated Calcium Carbonate
PIF	Public Investment Fund
PSU	Practical Salinity Unit
PUB	Public Utilities Board (Singapore)
PV	Photovoltaic
R&D	Research and Development
RDI	Research, Development, and Innovation
SASO	Saudi Standards, Metrology and Quality Organization
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SEC	Specific Energy Consumption
SIDF	Saudi Industrial Development Fund
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
SWA	Saudi Water Authority
SWIC	Saudi Water Innovation Center
SWPC	Saudi Water Partnership Company
TDS	Total Dissolved Solids
WTIIRA	Water Technologies Innovation Institute and Research Advancement

Executive Summary

Saudi Arabia's water sector is undergoing a transformative evolution, propelled by innovation and a strategic commitment to addressing water scarcity while advancing economic diversification. The Saudi Water Authority (SWA), through its innovation arms, the Water Technologies Innovation Institute & Research Advancement (WTIIRA) and the Saudi Water Innovation Centre (SWIC) is building a comprehensive ecosystem that integrates advanced technologies, robust regulatory frameworks, and global partnerships.

The Global Innovation Prize and is set to launch the Global Water Innovation Platform, a pioneering initiative to foster the development of cutting-edge solutions ensuring water security and sustainability. This strategic movement aligns seamlessly with Vision 2030, which emphasizes resource efficiency, technological leadership, and economic resilience.

The Kingdom's innovation value chain in the water sector extends from research and development (R&D) and pilot-scale testing to commercialization and large-scale deployment. SWA's initiatives transcend national boundaries, positioning Saudi Arabia as a global frontrunner in sustainable water management. Investment in smart infrastructure, accelerated water reuse, and regulatory modernization forms the foundation of this transformation.

Emerging trends—such as artificial intelligence (AI) optimization, renewable energy integration, and zero-liquid discharge (ZLD) technologies, offer new opportunities to enhance operational efficiency and minimize environmental impacts. Landmark projects such as like the solar-powered Al Khafji desalination plant, and the Haql brine mining initiative exemplify this vision, with plans to achieve 50% renewable-powered desalination capacity by 2030.

On a global scale, SWA's innovations contribute to water sustainability by improving desalination efficiency, reducing carbon emissions, and fostering knowledge exchange through international collaboration. Domestically, these advancements drive economic diversification by localizing technologies, creating high-value jobs, and transforming brine waste into valuable minerals such as lithium and magnesium.

In conclusion, Saudi Arabia's water sector innovation embodies the convergence of technological progress, environmental stewardship, and economic growth. By addressing current challenges and embracing future opportunities, the Kingdom is not only securing its water future but also setting a global benchmark for sustainable resource management and responsible innovation.

01

REPORT OBJECTIVES

This report aims to present a comprehensive analysis of innovation in Saudi Arabia's water sector, focusing on how structured innovation processes contribute to addressing national water challenges while reinforcing the Kingdom's leadership in sustainable resource management [9].

The specific objectives of the report are to:

Analyze the Innovation Value Chain: Examine how emerging water technologies are identified, tested, commercialized, and scaled within Saudi Arabia's evolving innovation ecosystem.

Assess the National Innovation Ecosystem: Explore the role of the Saudi Water Authority (SWA) as the central enabler coordinating research, funding pilot projects, and facilitating large-scale technological deployment aligned with Vision 2030 objectives.

Evaluate Adoption and Implementation Pathways: Investigate how promising technologies transition from research labs and pilot trials to full-scale implementation, emphasizing barriers, enablers, and success factors.

Recommend Acceleration Strategies: Propose actionable measures to enhance the integration of desalination efficiency, digital water systems, wastewater recycling, and resource circularity into the Kingdom's water infrastructure.

By fulfilling these objectives, the report provides a strategic framework to strengthen Saudi Arabia's position as a global leader in sustainable water innovation and resource management.

02

INTRODUCTION

Innovation lies at the heart of addressing water scarcity, one of the most critical global challenges of the 21st century. In arid regions such as Saudi Arabia, where natural water resources are extremely limited, the development and implementation of innovative and sustainable management strategies, are vital to ensuring long-term resilience, environmental stewardship, and economic growth. As the Kingdom faces increasing pressures from population growth, rapid industrialization, and climate change, its strategic focus on innovation aligns closely with the objectives of Vision 2030, which prioritizes diversification, sustainability, and localization as key pillars of national advancement [8].

Saudi Arabia's water innovation initiatives encompass the entire value chain, integrating cutting-edge research, industrial collaboration, and targeted investment. Core priorities include enhancing desalination efficiency, expanding wastewater reuse, and advancing digital water management. Through close cooperation among research institutions, technology developers, utilities, and policymakers, the Kingdom continues to build a robust and adaptive water ecosystem that strengthens sustainability and operational resilience.

The Saudi Water Innovation Centre (SWIC) plays a pivotal role in a nurturing environment for technical entrepreneurship and actively promotes international partnerships to stimulate collaborative innovation. through the Global Innovation Prize program[8]. Complementing these efforts, SWIC launched the Global Water Innovation Platform (GWIP) which aims to accelerate the creation of transformative solutions for global water resource management. The platform fosters collaboration among researchers, industry experts, and private enterprises, providing a forum to share and develop forward-thinking ideas. By remaining adaptive to technological advancements and developmental priorities, it ensures continuous alignment with the goals of Vision 2030, reinforcing Saudi Arabia's leadership in sustainable and innovative water management. Meanwhile, research arm of Saudi water authority, Water Technologies Innovation Institute and Research Advancement (WTIIRA) is conducting research (R&D) at lab scale as well as pilot scale for developing new technologies for water industry. WTIIRA aims to focuses on R&D and partnerships with academic institutions and industry. This institute also provides support to SWIC to achieve their goals.

Innovation in the water sector represents a systematic and strategic process rather than an isolated event. It encompasses a continuum of stages including scouting, lab testing, piloting, commercialization, and scaling designed to address complex challenges related to water security and sustainability. Unlike other industries where innovation may arise within a single domain, water innovation depends on cross-sectoral collaboration involving government bodies, research institutions, and private enterprises. This integrated approach ensures that new technologies transition efficiently from conceptual development to widespread application, strengthening both sustainability and resilience within the water management framework.

Saudi Arabia has adopted a comprehensive innovation value chain to drive progress in its water sector, ensuring that each phase of technological development is seamlessly linked, (see Figure 1). The process begins with scouting, where critical challenges such as desalination efficiency, wastewater reuse, and digital water management are identified. It progresses to piloting, where innovative solutions undergo rigorous validation and field testing in WTIIRA at Jubail. Successful pilots advance to commercialization, facilitated through public-private partnerships and targeted investment initiatives. Figure 2 shows the research and innovation pillar for operating and funding model of SWA the final phase—scaling—integrates proven innovations into the national water infrastructure, ensuring optimized performance, operational efficiency, and long-term resilience [3].

By aligning research priorities with water industry needs and national policy objectives, SWA ensures that innovation leads to measurable advancements in efficiency, sustainability, and resource optimization. This well-coordinated innovation value chain, supported by a robust ecosystem of stakeholders, not only enhances water security, but also fosters adaptability in response to evolving environmental and economic conditions.

THE INNOVATION VALUE CHAIN IN THE WATER SECTOR

Figure 1. Innovation value chain in the water sector [3].

Figure 2. Research and Innovation Pillar: Operating and funding model of SWA [8].

The Value Chain from Scouting to Scaling: The Technology Adoption Process

The progression from research and innovation to large-scale technology adoption in Saudi Arabia’s water sector follows a carefully structured and strategic framework. This pathway ensures that ground-breaking concepts are systematically developed, validated, and integrated into operational systems that strengthen national water security and sustainability. The process is built around four interlinked phases: Scouting and Research, Piloting and Technology Validation, Commercialization and Early Market Entry, and Scaling and Impact Assessment – which together form the core of the Kingdom’s National Innovation Value Chain. Each stage contributes uniquely to transforming innovative ideas into viable, market-ready technologies that align with Saudi Arabia’s Vision 2030 goals and the National Water Strategy.

01 Scouting & Research

The Scouting and Research phase forms the intellectual and technical foundation of Saudi Arabia’s water innovation ecosystem. It focuses on identifying technological gaps, generating new scientific knowledge, and developing next-generation solutions for desalination, wastewater treatment, and sustainable water resource management. This stage is where ideas are conceptualized, feasibility is assessed, and pilot-worthy innovations are born.

Given Saudi Arabia’s heavy dependence on desalination to meet its freshwater needs, research initiatives are strategically directed toward reducing energy intensity, improving process efficiency, and enhancing environmental sustainability. The Kingdom aims to revolutionize water treatment through materials innovation, process optimization, and digital transformation, ensuring that emerging technologies are both cost-effective and climate-resilient.

To achieve these goals, the country has developed a comprehensive R&D ecosystem that connects governmental agencies, research institutes, industry partners, and global collaborators. This ecosystem is coordinated under the Saudi Water Authority (SWA) and the Water Technologies Innovation Institute and Research Advancement (WTIIRA), which serve as national hubs for applied research and technology development. Their mandate includes fostering interdisciplinary collaborations across chemistry, materials science, process engineering, and data analytics to accelerate innovation from the laboratory to field-scale deployment [17].

Additionally, targeted research programs are addressing critical challenges such as:

- Developing low-energy desalination membranes and hybrid treatment systems.
- Advancing brine valorization and resource recovery technologies.
- Integrating AI and digital twins for intelligent process monitoring.
- Enhancing circular economy approaches through wastewater reuse and industrial symbiosis.

Through such initiatives, Saudi Arabia is not only closing the gap between academic research and industrial application but also positioning itself as a global leader in sustainable water innovation.

A summary of the key research areas, thematic groups, and institutional collaborations that constitute this ecosystem is illustrated in Figure 3 [7].

Processes & Products Innovation

Advanced membrane technologies

Integration of two-dimensional (2D) materials

Emerging contaminants and wastewater treatment

AI-supported monitoring and prediction of processes and operations

Process optimization and efficiency improvement

Circular Economy

Ion Separation Using Membrane Technology

Utilization of Sludge from Wastewater Treatment

Electrodialysis

Crystallization Techniques and Brine Concentration

Waste-to-Energy Conversion

Reuse and Recycling of Reverse Osmosis Membranes

Clean & Renewable Energy

Concentrated Solar Power and Photovoltaics

Geothermal and Wind Energy

Emerging contaminants and wastewater treatment

AI-supported monitoring and prediction of processes and operations

Process optimization and efficiency improvement

Sustainability & Advanced Materials

Electrochemical Technologies for Water Desalination and Treatment

Water Quality

Development of Engineering Materials Related to Water

Figure 3. Areas and Research Groups of WTIIRA-SWA. [7]

Research Groups

Research arm of SWA is consists of four research groups which includes, process & products innovation, clean & renewable energy, circular economy and sustainable materials & membranes. Each group plays a vital role in the development and testing of new technologies for water industry. Details description on each research group is provided below.

Process & Products Innovation

This research group is dedicated to advancing knowledge and technology across four key domains: Physical Processes, Chemical Processes, Biological Processes, and Membrane Processes. Figure 4 shows the process innovation group strategies for the research in WTIIRA. Together, these areas form the scientific and technical foundation for improving water quality, optimizing treatment efficiency, and fostering innovation across the water sector. In the domain of Physical Processes, the group concentrates on enhancing filtration and pre-treatment systems, which are vital for protecting downstream units and ensuring consistent operational performance. This includes optimizing sedimentation, coagulation, and particulate removal, to reduce fouling and energy consumption in subsequent treatment stages [8].

The Chemical Processes theme addresses a broad spectrum of challenges related to irrigation water purification, industrial wastewater management, brine treatment, and the mitigation of non-revenue water losses. Researchers in this area work on developing advanced oxidation techniques, chemical conditioning strategies, and environmentally sustainable solutions that minimize chemical usage and waste generation.

Within the Biological Processes stream, the focus lies on understanding and controlling biofouling, mitigating algal blooms, and optimizing biochemical reactions for nutrient removal and organic degradation. This research contributes to developing biologically driven treatment systems that enhance process stability and resilience under varying water quality conditions [10].

The Membrane Processes theme emphasizes advanced separation technologies such as reverse osmosis (RO), nanofiltration (NF), and emerging hybrid membrane systems. Efforts are directed toward improving membrane performance, developing regeneration and cleaning protocols, and integrating process automation and control to extend membrane lifespan and reduce operational costs.

By combining multidisciplinary expertise across these four domains, the group aims to advance sustainable water treatment technologies, ensure compliance with national and international water quality standards, and drive innovation within the Kingdom’s water research ecosystem [8].

Figure 4. Process innovation strategies for the research in WTIIRA

Clean and Renewable Energy

It is crucial to explore clean and renewable energy options for the water sector. This research group is dedicated to incorporating innovative technologies to promote sustainable water production and lower carbon emissions. This group focuses on five primary research domains related to clean and renewable energy in the water sector, as shown in Figure 5 [9].

Figure 5. Areas covered by the Clean and Renewable Energy group. [9]

Figure 5 illustrates the integrated framework for advancing sustainable energy solutions in the water sector, emphasizing the convergence of renewable energy, clean fuels, energy storage, clean energy systems, and smart infrastructure. Figure 5 also highlights the utilization of solar and wind power to drive desalination and water treatment. Solar technologies such as photovoltaic (PV) and concentrated solar power (CSP) systems are combined in hybrid PV–CSP configurations to ensure a continuous energy supply and improve reliability.

Similarly, wind energy is leveraged, particularly in regions with high-capacity factors, to support hybrid PV–Wind systems for stable power generation. The Clean Fuels domain focuses on decarbonisation through carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) and the development of green hydrogen via electrolysis driven by renewable sources. This approach aims to use hydrogen as both an energy carrier and a storage medium for desalination powered by renewable energy.

Figure 5 also addresses the intermittency of renewable energy by developing advanced storage technologies, including fluid-based and sodium-ion batteries, while optimizing the integration of battery systems with solar energy to ensure reliable power for desalination plants. The Clean Energy category explores emerging zero-emission technologies such as Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) providing a carbon-free electricity source to desalination facilities and Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFCs) for efficient, clean energy generation in the water sector. Finally, the Smart Infrastructure component focuses on digital transformation through AI-powered dashboards for real-time data analysis and smart grid integration, which enables distributed renewable energy systems to operate efficiently and ensure optimal water-energy management. Collectively, the figure presents a comprehensive roadmap that aligns technological innovation with sustainability goals to achieve carbon-neutral, resilient, and intelligent water infrastructure systems.

Renewable Energy ●

Solar Energy: Utilizing solar power (PV and CSP) for desalination and water treatment. This involves optimizing hybrid PV-CSP systems to provide a continuous energy supply and creating capacity factor maps to inform strategic deployment.

● Clean Fuels

CCUS: Capturing CO2 from power generation plants for use in the post-treatment of seawater reverse osmosis (SWRO) or applying Direct Air Capture (DAC) technology to attain carbon-negative desalination.

Green Hydrogen: Producing green hydrogen via electrolysis driven by renewable energy sources. This encompasses evaluating electrolyzers with varying water qualities, using hydrogen to energize RO plants, and exploring hydrogen as a means of energy storage for desalination powered by renewable energy.

Energy Storage ●

Development: Developing and testing advanced energy storage technologies, including fluid-based systems and sodium-ion batteries, to address the intermittency of renewable energy sources.

Integration: Optimizing the integration of renewable energy sources, such as PV, with various battery technologies to ensure a reliable power supply for desalination plants.

● Clean Energy

SMR: Exploring the viability and optimal configuration of Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) for powering desalination plants as a carbon-free electricity source.

SOFC: Investigating the possibility of Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFCs) for efficient and clean energy generation in the water sector.

Figure 6. Different energy sectors covered by renewable energy group. [12]

Circular Economy

The Circular Economy Research Group’s primary mission is to transition from a traditional linear model toward a circular framework that emphasizes resource recovery, recycling, and reuse. This approach aims to optimize the utilization of natural resources while minimizing environmental impacts across the entire water lifecycle [9].

The key objectives of the Circular Economy Research Group at WTIIRA include:

Enhancing water efficiency: Developing solutions to optimize water usage and reduce wastewater generation and disposal.

Resource valorization: Recovering valuable materials and minerals from seawater brine to strengthen the national economy.

Maximizing waste utilization: Transforming waste into usable resources to advance environmental protection and long-term water system sustainability.

Ion separation and concentration: Investigating advanced processes for the selective recovery of critical minerals from sea-water brine.

Innovation and technology promotion: Encouraging the development and application of novel ideas and technologies that drive progress toward a sustainable circular water economy.

Figure 7. Circular economy cycle by circular economy cycle. [9]

A central focus is the prevention and management of disinfection by-products through the application of advanced purification and disinfection technologies. Leveraging state-of-the-art analytical instrumentation, WTIIRA researchers perform detailed water quality analyses across production and transmission systems throughout the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, ensuring alignment with national and international standards.

In addition, the Sustainability & Advanced Materials Group at WTIIRA aims to accelerate innovation in sustainable water treatment and resource recovery through the following objectives:

Development of advanced materials: Design and synthesis of next-generation membranes, adsorbents, catalysts, and coatings for enhanced water and wastewater treatment performance.

Sustainable process design: Integrating eco-efficient technologies and low-carbon materials to minimize energy consumption and environmental footprint across treatment processes.

Circular material utilization: Promoting the reuse and recycling of process materials and by-products to support circular economy principles within the water sector.

Performance optimization and lifecycle assessment: Conducting comprehensive assessments of material durability, environmental impact, and long-term sustainability.

Collaborative innovation: Partnering with academia, industry, and government bodies to translate laboratory-scale advancements into scalable, real-world water treatment and sustainability solutions.

Sustainability and Advanced Materials

03
Research Groups

This group integrates multidisciplinary expertise to ensure that freshwater quality standards are achieved through biological, chemical, and metallurgical engineering perspectives. At WTIIRA, researchers and specialists focus on identifying and mitigating current and emerging risks to water quality, including those associated with contaminants, climate change, and evolving operational practices.

Figure 8. Sustainability & Advanced Materials Group Objectives in WTIIRA. [9]

Overall, WTIIRA has made significant achievements during the year 2025. The first is the successful completion of numerous research projects and the signing of multiple local and international research agreements. These milestones reflect WTIIRA’s strong commitment to driving innovation, sustainability, and global collaboration in the water and environmental sectors. WTIIRA has completed 150 research projects across a wide range of fields. These include sustainability, advanced materials, process innovation, clean and renewable energy, and the circular economy [12]. Each project represents a strategic step toward developing practical solutions that address pressing environmental and industrial challenges. The diversity of research domains also underscores WTIIRA’s multidisciplinary approach and its alignment with national and global sustainability goals. WTIIRA has signed 42 research agreements with both local and international partners. These agreements play a crucial role in fostering collaboration, enabling knowledge transfer, and strengthening the institute’s global research network. Through such partnerships, WTIIRA not only expands its technical expertise but also contributes to the broader advancement of innovative water technologies worldwide [12].

Overall, WTIIRA’s progress and leadership in scientific research and collaboration demonstrates how the institute continues to position itself as a driving force in advancing sustainable technologies, promoting circular economy principles, and supporting Saudi Arabia’s Vision 2030 objectives for innovation and environmental stewardship.

Water Research Community (WRC)

The Water Research Community (WRC) of the Saudi Water Authority (SWA) under WTIIRA was established as a national platform to unite researchers, universities, and industry experts around real operational challenges in the Kingdom’s water sector. Its purpose is to coordinate research effort, strengthen partnerships with national and international institutions, and align academic work with Saudi Arabia’s strategic priorities in desalination, water transmission, distribution, wastewater treatment, resource recovery, and the circular economy. Through regular forums hosted with leading universities such as KAU, KFUPM, University of Tabuk, and Khalifa University, the WRC has grown into a recognized hub for scientific exchange, showcasing innovations, technical discussions, and collaborative opportunities.

The impact of the WRC is already visible across the sector. It has broken institutional silos by creating a shared space for utilities, regulators, researchers, and private-sector innovators to work together on targeted solutions. Each edition attracts hundreds of participants and dozens of research proposals, building national capacity and accelerating idea generation.

The initiative strengthens Saudi Arabia's innovation ecosystem by promoting advanced membranes, energy–water nexus technologies, AI-driven digital water tools, and circular-economy solutions. It also supports talent development by engaging students and early-career researchers in poster sessions, competitions, and joint project development, directly contributing to the Kingdom's Vision 2030 goals for knowledge-based economic growth.

Through the WRC, WTIIRA and SWA have received a strong pipeline of research projects and ideas across key thematic areas. These include new membrane materials and NF/RO process innovations, brine concentration and valorization concepts, renewable energy–powered water treatment systems, AI-driven monitoring and digital twins for desalination and networks, and community-level initiatives for water conservation. Notable examples include the composite membrane development project with KFUPM, renewable-energy prototype systems from Tabuk, and multiple digital water proposals showcased at recent forums. Altogether, the Water Research Community is establishing itself as the Kingdom's main gateway for connecting scientific research with real-world water-sector needs.

Figure 9. Water Research community initiative by WTIIRA-SWA. [8]

02 Piloting and Technology Validation

Before a technology can be integrated into Saudi Arabia's water infrastructure, it must first demonstrate efficiency, sustainability, and economic feasibility in alignment with the Kingdom's Vision 2030 sustainability goals [6]. This ensures that only technologies capable of contributing to long-term environmental and economic resilience are adopted on a national scale. At the center of this phase stands the Saudi Water Innovation Center (SWIC), which acts as the Kingdom's primary platform for piloting and validating emerging water technologies. SWIC plays a pivotal role in de-risking innovation by providing advanced infrastructure, technical expertise, and regulatory guidance throughout the testing and prototyping process.

Saudi Arabia has established a comprehensive and collaborative system for pilot testing and validation that integrates the efforts of government entities, research institutions, and private-sector partners. Through state-funded pilot programs, real-world testing initiatives, and international collaborations, the Kingdom ensures that new technologies, particularly in desalination, wastewater treatment, and water resource management are optimized for performance and reliability before large-scale adoption. This structured approach strengthens confidence in innovation, accelerates technology readiness, and supports the national goal of achieving sustainable water security.

Validating Research Findings into Prototype Systems

Validated research findings are then transformed into prototype systems through research institutions such as King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (KAUST) and the Water Technologies Innovation Institute and Research Advancement [8].

These institutions conduct detailed laboratory-scale assessments under simulated operational conditions using specialized desalination testbeds, controlled feedwater compositions, and advanced real-time monitoring systems. While these early validation efforts are critical for establishing the technical feasibility of innovations, bridging the gap between laboratory research and real-world application often requires additional institutional and financial support.

The Saudi Water Innovation Center (SWIC) extends this process by providing pilot testing opportunities and early-stage market validation. Through its innovation and incubation programs, SWIC assists startups and technology developers, in refining their prototype systems, performing field trials, and gaining hands-on mentorship from industry experts, investors, and regulatory specialists. These mentorship activities are central to SWIC's pilot testing model, helping innovators strengthen their business models, improve their value propositions, and navigate regulatory and market entry pathways effectively. This integrated approach ensures that promising technologies transition efficiently from research and development to commercialization, contributing directly to the Kingdom's water innovation ecosystem.

Key Components of Testing

There are three essential components that form the foundation of desalination technology testing and development: Desalination Testbeds, Controlled Feedwater Compositions, and Real-Time Monitoring Equipment. Desalination testbeds serve as controlled environments where new desalination technologies are evaluated under simulated operational conditions. These platforms enable researchers to assess system efficiency, energy consumption, and long-term durability before implementing solutions on a larger scale. Controlled feedwater compositions involve adjusting the chemical and physical properties of input water—such as salinity, temperature, and organic content, to replicate the conditions found in real desalination plants.

This approach helps researchers understand system resilience and optimize treatment processes for varying water qualities. Real-time monitoring equipment incorporates advanced sensors and data analytics tools to track key performance indicators, including membrane fouling, energy efficiency, and water recovery rates. By providing immediate feedback and valuable insights, these systems allow for timely operational adjustments and contribute to the effective scaling of desalination technologies. Together, these three components ensure that innovations in desalination are thoroughly validated, efficient, and sustainable before their widespread deployment [8].

Testing Under Controlled Conditions

Pilot testing and controlled trials play a critical role in validating the technical and economic feasibility of emerging water technologies before full-scale deployment. These tests are conducted at dedicated pilot facilities managed by WTIIRA and the Water Desalination, where desalination and wastewater treatment solutions undergo rigorous evaluation under simulated real-world conditions [6]. An example of this infrastructure is shown in Figure 10, which depicts the pilot stations at the Jubail plant.

To complement these efforts, WTIIRA provides its testing infrastructure to both SWA and the Water Desalination, supporting the assessment of innovative water treatment technologies [3]. Meanwhile, SWIC serves as a dedicated platform for startups which help refine early-stage innovations and prepare them for industrial application. By integrating AI-driven monitoring systems and process automation, WTIIRA enhances the validation process, ensuring that new desalination and wastewater treatment solutions meet efficiency and sustainability benchmarks before progressing to large-scale deployment. Before full-scale deployment, technology must achieve key performance benchmarks [8].

Figure 10. Pilot plant at the Jubail under WTIIRA Source: [23].

Advanced Monitoring Technologies

SWA has adopted advanced monitoring and analytics technologies to enhance operational transparency, predictive performance, and environmental compliance within pilot testing programs by WTIIRA. These technologies form the foundation of a data-driven approach toward water resource management and desalination optimization.

- **Remote Sensing Systems**

Satellite imagery and drone-based assessments are employed to monitor the environmental impacts of water infrastructure projects. These systems provide continuous insight into changes in coastal and terrestrial ecosystems, supporting sustainable development and regulatory compliance [6].

- **Automated Sensor Networks**

IoT-enabled devices deployed in desalination facilities continuously record parameters such as temperature, salinity, and pressure. The real-time data generated enables predictive maintenance and operational reliability [12].

- **AI-Powered Predictive Analytics**

Machine learning algorithms analyze historical operational data to forecast potential system malfunctions, thereby minimizing downtime, improving plant reliability, and extending asset life-cycles [14].

- **Brine Discharge Monitoring Systems**

These systems assess brine concentration levels to ensure adherence to environmental standards, and mitigate the ecological impact of discharge activities on marine biodiversity [6].

Assessing Scalability Before Full-Scale Implementation

To ensure that desalination technologies are successfully commercialized and integrated into Saudi Arabia's national water infrastructure, scalability assessment plays a vital role. The SWA in collaboration with the WTIIRA, conducts detailed feasibility studies and pilot demonstrations to evaluate technological readiness before large-scale implementation. These evaluations are carried out at leading research facilities such as WTIIRA and at demonstration sites, including the brine mining pilot plant in Haql. Scalability assessment focuses on three key evaluation criteria that determine a technology's operational, economic, and environmental viability under Saudi Arabia's unique climatic and infrastructure conditions.

Energy Consumption Reduction Potential

This criterion examines how effectively advanced desalination technologies can reduce energy demands and operational costs. Research emphasizes the role of energy-efficient reverse osmosis (RO) systems and high-performance energy recovery devices in improving desalination efficiency. Such innovations directly contribute to national sustainability goals by minimizing the carbon footprint of large-scale desalination plants [4].

Membrane Performance at Scale

Membrane technologies undergo rigorous testing to evaluate durability, fouling resistance, and long-term operational stability under real-world conditions. These studies are essential for confirming that laboratory-scale efficiencies can be replicated in industrial settings. The MEWA supports such validation to ensure the reliability of large-scale applications over prolonged operational cycles.

Infrastructure Adaptability

This assessment focuses on the integration of new desalination systems into Saudi Arabia's existing water networks. It considers both technical compatibility and the potential for co-benefits, such as mineral extraction from desalination brine, to promote resource recovery. This criterion ensures that novel technologies align with national infrastructure strategies and enhance the overall sustainability of the water sector [2].

By systematically addressing these evaluation areas, Saudi Arabia strengthens its capacity to scale promising desalination technologies from pilot plants to full-scale industrial adoption, thereby advancing its Vision 2030 objectives of innovation, efficiency, and environmental stewardship.

03 Commercialization and Early Market Entry

The Commercialization and Scaling phase ensures that validated water technologies transition from pilot testing to full-scale deployment in industrial, municipal, and national water infrastructure. This phase is essential for securing financial investments, obtaining regulatory approvals, and fostering industry adoption, to integrate cutting-edge desalination, wastewater treatment, and water management solutions across Saudi Arabia.

The Saudi Water Partnership Company (SWPC) and Water Desalination spearhead public-private partnerships (PPPs) to scale water solutions in alignment with Vision 2030 objectives [15]. Supporting these national-level efforts, the Saudi Water Innovation Center (SWIC) plays a central role in enabling early-stage companies to reach market readiness. By offering tailored incubation and investment readiness programs, SWIC helps transform validated technologies into commercially viable solutions adopted by both government and industry.

Figure 11. Commercial scale RO plant for desalination in Saudi Water Partnership Company (SWPC).

SWIC’s Incubation Model and Commercialization Support

The Saudi Water Innovation Center (SWIC) plays a fundamental role in bridging the gap between early-stage research and large-scale commercialization. Through its structured incubation model, SWIC provides targeted support that enables water technology startups to validate, refine, and commercialize their solutions in alignment with Saudi Arabia’s Vision 2030 objectives.

Key Incubation Programs

Soft-Landing Program

Assists international startups in establishing a presence in Saudi Arabia by providing market entry support, regulatory guidance, and strategic business development assistance [3].

Prototyping and Validation Support

Provides access to specialized testing facilities for refining prototypes and conducting proof-of-concept studies before market deployment [3].

Investment Readiness Accelerator

Helps startups prepare for fundraising rounds by refining their business models and connecting them with venture capital firms, private equity investors, and government funding programs.

Industry Matchmaking & Market Expansion

Facilitates partnerships with major water sector stakeholders, including NEOM, ACWA Power, and the Red Sea Authority, ensuring that innovative technologies secure large-scale adoption.

Figure 12. Key incubation program by SWIC.

Structured Commercialization Programs

Building on this incubation foundation, SWIC offers a suite of structured engagement programs designed to accelerate the transition from validated prototypes to full-scale industry adoption. These programs provide startups with critical commercialization support, ensuring readiness for investment, regulatory alignment, and market deployment [3].

SWIC highlights four main engagement activities [3]:

- **Demo Days**

Platforms where start-ups present their validated technologies to investors, government agencies, and commercial partners. The aim is to attract funding, partnerships, and pilot opportunities.

- **Pitchathons**

Competitive pitching events that challenge start-ups to refine their value propositions and demonstrate the market potential of their innovations, often leading to investment commitments.

- **Mentorship Hours**

Direct sessions with industry leaders, technical experts, and investors who offer strategic advice on scaling, operational efficiency, and navigating regulatory frameworks.

- **Workshops and Training Sessions**

Tailored sessions focusing on business development topics such as financial structuring, intellectual property rights, international market access, and operational scalability.

Together, these initiatives ensure that innovative water technologies are investment-ready, regulatorily compliant, and prepared for market deployment, supporting Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 innovation ecosystem.

Figure 13. Strategic mentorship session between startups and experts during the Water Technology Works program [3].

Strategic Investments and Industry Adoption

Saudi Arabia is driving large-scale water innovation adoption through strategic investments and industry partnerships. This section highlights the transition from research and pilot projects to commercial implementation, led by government agencies and research institutions.

It outlines three major developments:

Public–Private Partnerships in Desalination: The Saudi Water Partnership Company (SWPC) is promoting collaboration between the public and private sectors by awarding multiple desalination projects to Independent Water Producers (IWPs). This approach enhances efficiency, reduces costs, and ensures sustainable desalination growth.

Water Desalination Leadership in Energy Efficiency: The Water Desalination has prioritized reverse osmosis (RO) technology over traditional thermal methods, achieving a 62% reduction in emissions and energy use. Projects like the Al Khafji RO Desalination Plant exemplify Saudi Arabia’s leadership in energy-efficient desalination [16].

Innovations in Desalination and Brine Mining: The WTIIRA is pioneering low-energy membrane brine concentration and selective electrodialysis to extract valuable minerals from brine. These technologies transform desalination waste into economic.

Overall, this framework demonstrates how Saudi Arabia integrates research, innovation, and investment to establish a sustainable, efficient, and economically viable water industry ecosystem under Vision 2030 [12].

International Partnerships in Water Commercialization

Building on its domestic scale-up success, Saudi Arabia is forming global partnerships to integrate innovation, improve efficiency, and extract more value from water treatment processes. It highlights two major international initiatives:

01 Brine Mining Innovation – Saudi Arabia has partnered with UralTechProm (Russia) to enhance brine mining technologies. This collaboration focuses on extracting valuable minerals such as lithium, magnesium, and potassium from desalination waste streams. The initiative supports both resource recovery and economic diversification, turning waste into high-value products [12].

02 AI and Automation in Water Management: The Kingdom has established a partnership with Schneider Electric (France) to introduce AI-driven automation in desalination plants. This includes smart process control to improve efficiency, reduce energy consumption, and enable predictive maintenance [5].

Together, these partnerships demonstrate Saudi Arabia’s strategic approach to global technology integration, promoting innovation in sustainable water management, while strengthening international cooperation aligned with Vision 2030.

Assessing Economic and Environmental Viability

Before new technologies are commercialized, Saudi Arabia ensures that new water technologies are economically feasible, environmentally sustainable, and ready for large-scale commercialization before deployment.

The assessment framework focuses on three critical evaluation pillars:

Operational Efficiency:

This involves measuring how new technologies improve energy consumption, water recovery, and overall costs compared to conventional desalination systems. It uses metrics like Specific Energy Consumption (SEC) to calculate the energy required to produce one cubic meter of desalinated water. These evaluations help decision-makers determine the performance efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and sustainability of technologies at scale.

Regulatory Compliance:

Every technology must align with environmental and operational standards set by MEWA (Ministry of Environment, Water, and Agriculture) and SASO (Saudi Standards, Metrology and Quality Organization). Additionally, these standards are benchmarked against global frameworks from the International Water Association (IWA) and the World Bank, ensuring that Saudi technologies meet international expectations for environmental protection and safety.

Market Readiness:

This assessment determines whether a technology is financially viable and commercially scalable. It involves economic feasibility studies, investment potential analysis, and risk evaluations, considering factors such as capital cost, regulatory barriers, and market price volatility. These studies ensure strong private-sector participation and long-term investment confidence.

In summary, this section highlights Saudi Arabia's systematic approach to commercialization, ensuring that technologies are not only technically sound but also economically practical, environmentally responsible, and market-ready before full-scale adoption.

04 Scaling and Impact Assessment

The final stage of the water innovation value chain brings together two essential dimensions which include large-scale deployment of validated technologies and continuous monitoring of their long-term performance and impact. On the one hand, WTIIRA and SWIC ensures that successful pilots are integrated into national infrastructure, expanding desalination, wastewater treatment, and distribution capabilities through coordinated action by SWA, NWC, and MEWA, in collaboration with global partners. On the other hand, impact assessment guarantees that these technologies deliver sustained efficiency, environmental compliance, and resilience by embedding AI-driven monitoring, IoT-based optimization, and robust KPIs into daily operations. By combining implementation with performance evaluation, Saudi Arabia ensures that innovation does not stop at adoption.

Figure 14. Waste-water treatment handled by NWC.

Scaling and Expansion Implementation

Scaling and expansion is a critical stage in integrating advanced water technologies into Saudi Arabia’s infrastructure, ensuring efficient water management and long-term sustainability. This phase involves scaling up validated technological solutions, enforcing regulatory compliance, and optimizing operational efficiency across desalination plants, wastewater treatment facilities, and water distribution networks.

A coordinated regulatory framework is essential for enabling the effective deployment of new water technologies. In Saudi Arabia, MEWA, SWA, and NWC each contribute to strengthening governance and ensuring that innovation aligns with national sustainability objectives outlined in Vision 2030 [1].

Recognizing the role of international collaboration in accelerating technological advancements, Saudi Arabia actively engages with global organizations, development banks, and industry leaders to exchange best practices and integrate cutting-edge solutions into its national water system. This strategic approach aligns with the country’s broader vision of sustainable development and technological leadership.

Saudi Arabia is currently expanding its water sector capabilities through a series of targeted initiatives that align with its national innovation and sustainability objectives [11], [13]. These initiatives are summarized in Table 1, before being discussed in detail in the following subsections.

Table 1. Summary of implementation and expansion initiatives in Saudi Arabia’s water sector.

Implementation Area	Key Collaborators	Strategic Focus / Benefit
Energy-Efficient Desalination Expansion	NEDO (Japan), KAUST, Evove Ltd. (UK)	Deployment of high-recovery SWRO systems powered by renewable energy
Brine Mining & Resource Recovery	TAEKYUNG BK (South Korea), KMOU, WDC	Extraction of high-purity NaCl, Mg, vaterite type CaCO ₃ , and bromine from SWRO brine
AI-Driven Infrastructure Optimization	TOYOBO MC Corp. (Japan), KAUST, KFUPM	Predictive maintenance, automated leak detection, and smart control
National & Humanitarian Water Projects	KS Relief, NWC, Water Desalination	Integration of advanced technologies in NEOM, Red Sea, and mobile units

Energy-Efficient and Sustainable Desalination Expansion

Saudi Arabia continues to advance energy-efficient desalination technologies as part of its national sustainability ambitions under Vision 2030. Recent initiatives include the deployment of renewable-powered desalination systems, exemplified by the Al Khafji solar-powered RO plant, which significantly reduces emissions while producing 60,000 m³ of water per day. Complementing these efforts, WTIIRA is developing high-efficiency RO membranes and advanced fouling monitoring technologies to improve performance and reduce energy consumption across desalination operations [1] [12] [17].

Large-Scale Brine Mining and Resource Recovery

Saudi Arabia is advancing large-scale brine mining and resource recovery technologies through ongoing research and pilot programs led by WTIIRA. These efforts include the development of membrane-based concentration systems and technologies to recover minerals such as sodium chloride, calcium carbonate, and magnesium from desalination brine, supporting circular economy objectives [12].

AI-Driven Water Infrastructure Optimization

Saudi Arabia is increasingly integrating AI-driven technologies into desalination and water distribution networks. SWA has piloted predictive maintenance, automated leak detection, and smart process control systems that improve efficiency and reduce non-revenue water losses [5]. Research institutions such as KAUST also contribute to the development of intelligent monitoring and data analytics tools that support real-time optimization across water facilities [18].

Water Solutions for National and Humanitarian Projects

Saudi Arabia is deploying advanced water technologies across major national developments such as NEOM and The Red Sea Project, supporting the broader sustainability objectives of Vision 2030. In parallel, national agencies continue expanding mobile desalination capabilities to improve water access in underserved regions and enhance resilience during emergencies [1].

Operational Integration and Performance Optimization

Following regulatory approvals and commercialization, newly deployed water technologies must demonstrate sustained operational efficiency and environmental sustainability. This phase focuses on long-term performance monitoring, AI-driven process optimization, and predictive maintenance to ensure that water infrastructure remains cost-effective and aligned with Saudi Arabia’s sustainability goals [6].

AI-Powered Process Optimization: Advanced automated control systems leverage real-time data analytics to optimize desalination processes, adjust energy usage, and enhance membrane lifespan [6].

Smart Water Management Systems: IoT-based monitoring networks enable adaptive control over water distribution, pressure balancing, and leak prevention, thereby improving overall resource management [14].

Performance-Based Infrastructure Adjustments: Sensor-based operational data analysis is used to refine facility processes, minimize waste, and enhance water reuse efficiency [6].

Impact Monitoring and Performance Assessment

Impact monitoring and performance assessment is a critical component in evaluating the efficiency, sustainability, and economic viability of implemented water technologies. This phase ensures that the technologies yield measurable benefits, adhere to environmental regulations, and align with global best practices.

By leveraging real-time data collection, artificial intelligence (AI) applications, and adaptive policy measures, the Kingdom continuously refines and enhances its water management infrastructure. In this phase of the value chain, Saudi Arabia optimizes operational performance, minimize resource waste, and advance its sustainability agenda [6].

Figure 15. Water governance for impact monitoring and performance assessment

Saudi Arabia's Commitment to Performance Optimization

The Ministry of Environment, Water, and Agriculture (MEWA) and the Saudi Water Authority (SWA) lead the development of regulatory frameworks and performance monitoring systems that govern the country's desalination, wastewater treatment, and water distribution networks. While regulatory frameworks are established in earlier phases of the water innovation value chain, their continuous evaluation, adaptation, and enforcement remain critical in this phase to ensure that newly implemented technologies align with efficiency benchmarks, environmental compliance, and sustainability targets [14].

These agencies collaborate closely with research institutions like WTIIRA, KAUST, KAU, and private-sector entities, including ACWA Power and Schneider Electric, to define and monitor key performance indicators (KPIs).

These KPIs include:

- **Energy Consumption in Desalination Plants:** energy consumption at commercial desalination plant is 2.2kWh/m³. Meanwhile, 2.2kWh/m³ in pilot studies for water desalination [10].
- **Water Recovery Rates:** Aiming for a minimum efficiency of 50% in standard desalination plants, with advanced systems reaching 60-65% water recovery rates [6].
- **Brine Discharge Salinity Levels:** Ensuring salinity levels remain below 60 PSU (Practical Salinity Units) to minimize marine ecosystem disruption, aligning with global environmental benchmarks [14].

- **Plant Operational Efficiency and Uptime:** Setting a benchmark of 95% operational uptime, ensuring minimal disruptions in desalination and wastewater treatment operations [6].

Technology-Driven Performance Monitoring

Saudi Arabia has established a technologically advanced water monitoring ecosystem by leveraging artificial intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IoT)-enabled sensors, and digital twin technologies. These tools enhance real-time operational visibility, predictive maintenance, and automated system optimization, ensuring that desalination plants, wastewater treatment facilities, and water distribution networks meet performance and sustainability benchmarks. The Saudi Water Innovation Center (SWIC) plays a key role in advancing technology-driven monitoring solutions by integrating AI-powered analytics, post-incubation performance tracking, and collaborative research initiatives. Through its partnerships with SWA, NWC, and private-sector players, SWIC ensures that newly implemented water technologies undergo continuous performance validation and long-term impact assessment [3].

AI-Powered Monitoring Systems and Predictive Analytics

Machine learning algorithms analyze historical operational data to enable predictive maintenance and early fault detection, significantly reducing plant downtime [14]. By integrating automated control systems, desalination facilities have enhanced their predictive maintenance capabilities, achieving an 18% reduction in unplanned shutdowns and improved overall plant uptime [6].

SWIC actively supports post-deployment monitoring for start-ups, ensuring that their AI-driven solutions maintain operational efficiency and regulatory compliance. For example, SWIC-supported ventures such as Subsea-ROwind and Kumulus utilize AI-based analytics for real-time performance assessment and continuous system optimization [3].

Figure 16. Growth of AI in Water Management.

IoT-Based Smart Sensors for Real-Time Optimization

Smart sensors continuously monitor parameters such as temperature, salinity, and pressure, enabling real-time adjustments in desalination and wastewater treatment processes [8]. SWIC collaborates with desalination operators to deploy IoT-enabled efficiency monitoring systems, helping start-ups enhance technology performance beyond the pilot phase. For instance, Watercycle Technologies leverages SWIC's and WTIIRA post-implementation tracking network to assess brine mineral recovery efficiency and energy reduction outcomes [3]. These sensor-driven optimizations have contributed to a 10% reduction in energy consumption across Saudi Arabia's desalination sector [6].

Remote Sensing and Digital Twin Technology

Digital twin models replicate real-world desalination plant operations, providing predictive insights for process optimization and energy efficiency enhancement [14]. SWIC's digital twin initiatives integrate virtual frameworks into pilot projects, to ensure that new technologies meet long-term efficiency benchmarks prior to full-scale implementation [3].

Data Collection and Monitoring Systems

This process is executed through a network of advanced digital monitoring platforms, including:

- [SCADA \(Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition\) Systems](#)

These automated control systems collect, process, and analyze live operational data from desalination plants, tracking flow rates, energy consumption, and chemical dosing efficiency [6].

- [IoT-Enabled Sensor Networks](#)

These sensors are strategically deployed in pipelines, reservoirs, and desalination facilities, continuously measuring pressure, temperature, salinity, and potential leakages to detect inefficiencies before they escalate [14].

- [AI-Driven Remote Sensing and Digital Twin Technology](#)

By simulating the operation of water treatment plants in a digital environment, engineers can analyze historical and real-time performance trends, optimizing energy usage and predictive maintenance strategies [6]. WTIIRA has developed the brine mining process optimization software along with AI involvement via digital twin application which can contribute into the water desalination and brine mining industry.

Technology-Enabled Decision-Making and Optimization

Saudi Arabia leverages AI and predictive analytics to enhance decision-making processes within its water management framework. Data-driven operational insights allow for:

01 Dynamic Resource Allocation: AI models analyze real-time demand fluctuations and adjust water distribution patterns accordingly, preventing supply shortages in high-demand areas. This approach has improved water supply reliability by 20% in major urban centers such as Riyadh and Jeddah [6].

02 Energy Optimization in Desalination: Machine learning algorithms continuously analyze energy consumption patterns, optimizing desalination processes to reduce waste and improve sustainability. AI-driven adjustments in membrane cleaning cycles have contributed to a 10% decrease in energy use per cubic meter of desalinated water [14].

03 Climate Resilience Strategies: AI-based forecasting models use meteorological and hydrological data to predict seasonal variations in water demand, allowing plants to adjust production rates proactively and minimize operational strain [14].

Predictive Maintenance, Automated System Optimization, and Enhanced Response Mechanisms

Predictive Maintenance

AI-driven predictive maintenance systems continuously analyze sensor-generated data to detect early indicators of equipment degradation. By forecasting mechanical wear and operational anomalies, these intelligent algorithms enable proactive maintenance scheduling. This approach reduces unplanned equipment downtime by approximately 40% and extends the average operational lifespan of assets by 25% [6].

Automated System Optimization

Advanced digital control platforms leverage real-time operational data to automatically fine-tune system parameters, ensuring maximum efficiency and cost-effectiveness. Examples include:

01 Membrane Cleaning Optimization: Artificial intelligence determines the optimal cleaning frequency and chemical formulation for desalination membranes, minimizing maintenance downtime by 30% [14].

02 Energy Load Balancing: Smart energy management systems dynamically regulate power distribution across desalination operations, minimizing energy expenditure while maintaining peak process efficiency [6].

Enhanced Response Mechanisms

AI-enabled automated emergency response systems activate instantaneously upon detecting abnormal conditions, improving reliability and environmental compliance. Key applications include:

01 Immediate Leak Detection and Containment: Upon identifying pipeline anomalies, automated isolation protocols prevent large-scale water losses, achieving a 15% reduction in network leakage [14].

02 Real-Time Brine Discharge Monitoring: AI-based monitoring of salinity and effluent parameters ensures adherence to environmental regulations, significantly reducing the risk of excessive brine discharge into marine ecosystems [6].

The Water Oasis in Rabigh represents a pioneering national initiative dedicated to advancing research and innovation in sustainable water solutions. This initiative establishes a cutting-edge environment for scientists, specialists, and researchers, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration in the field of water and environmental technologies. By empowering institutions such as the WTIIRA, the Advanced Research Center, and the Saudi Water Innovation Center, the Oasis facilitates the translation of research into applied solutions through laboratory and pilot-scale projects. Equipped with state-of-the-art infrastructure and smart laboratories, it serves as a hub for testing, validation, and development of emerging technologies that address the Kingdom's critical water and environmental challenges [19].

Water Oasis Objectives

- **Enhance Scientific Research:**

Expand the scope of research to include advanced technologies across the water value chain, covering production, transportation, distribution, treatment, reuse, water resource management, and artificial intelligence applications.

- **Enable Innovation:**

Provide a dynamic environment for technology-driven companies, innovators, and entrepreneurs to develop, test, and commercialize new solutions within the water sector.

- **Activate Partnerships:**

Foster collaborative research and knowledge exchange through strategic partnerships with leading local and international universities, research centers, and institutes.

RABIGH RESEARCH AND INNOVATION WATER OASIS

- **Achieve Water and Environmental Sustainability:**

Support the Kingdom's long-term vision for sustainability by promoting resource efficiency, circular economy principles, and the achievement of national and global sustainable development goals related to water and energy.

Figure 17. Top view of Rabigh Water Oasis for Water Desalination.

State-of-the-Art Facilities & Labs

The Research and Technology Infrastructure at the Rabigh Water Oasis represents a cutting-edge ecosystem designed to accelerate innovation, foster interdisciplinary collaboration, and translate scientific research into practical water and environmental solutions. Each facility is equipped with advanced tools, pilot-scale setups, and digital integration systems to support end-to-end technology development.

Advanced Membrane Lab

- Develops high-performance membranes offering superior selectivity and reduced energy consumption.
- Facilitates prototype testing under variable salinity and temperature conditions, enabling robust performance evaluation.

AI & IoT Lab

- Enables real-time water quality monitoring through integrated sensors, data analytics, and AI-driven control systems.
- Develops predictive maintenance models to minimize operational downtime and optimize resource efficiency.

Brine Mining Lab

- Specializes in novel extraction and valorization of critical minerals from brine streams.
- Conducts pilot-scale testing of sustainable brine management strategies to reduce waste and environmental impact.

Renewable Energy Integration Lab

- Focuses on solar-driven desalination systems and hybrid wind-solar technologies for sustainable water production.
- Explores hydrogen-based processes to enable off-grid and low-carbon desalination operations.

Printing and Prototyping Lab

- Facilitates rapid fabrication of desalination components, sensor housings, and experimental tools.
- Supports real-time iteration and testing to accelerate technology deployment and scale-up.

Molecular and Biological Labs

- Conducts advanced studies in water quality, microbiology, and bioprocessing, contributing to safer and more efficient treatment methods.

Process Innovation Lab

- Drives desalination optimization to enhance efficiency and minimize environmental footprint.
- Develops advanced water treatment solutions and digitalized process control systems integrating AI and IoT technologies.

Collaboration Zones

- **Innovation Theatre:**

A dynamic venue (capacity 800+) for seminars, global water summits, and conferences aimed at sharing insights and fostering collaborative innovation.

- **Start-up Incubation Hub:**

A dedicated platform for prototyping, mentorship, and networking among emerging water-tech entrepreneurs and innovators.

- **Library and Digital Knowledge Centre:**

Provides access to global databases, digital learning tools, and interactive modules to support research and professional development.

- **Technology Showrooms:**

Showcases state-of-the-art water production, monitoring, and control technologies, enabling stakeholders to explore practical applications and system demonstrations.

Water Production Innovation in KSA

WTIIRA has led the way in embracing and advocating for new technologies in water treatment. Acknowledging the urgent demand for innovative approaches to tackle increasing issues of water scarcity and pollution, WTIIRA has launched multiple initiatives to foster the creation and application of advanced technologies [12].

- **Research and Development:** WTIIRA invests heavily in research and development to investigate new materials, processes, and technologies for water treatment. This involves partnerships with universities, research entities, and industry collaborators to promote innovation and accelerate the commercialization of new solutions.
- **Pilot Projects and Demonstrations:** To validate the performance and feasibility of emerging technologies, WTIIRA implements pilot projects and demonstrations in real-world settings. These projects provide valuable data and insights, enabling the optimization and scaling up of promising technologies.
- **Capacity Building and Training:** WTIIRA acknowledges the significance of enhancing skills and knowledge the water treatment sector. The organization offers training programs, workshops, and seminars to educate and empower professionals, policymakers, and communities about the latest technologies and best practices.
- **Policy Advocacy and Standards Development:** WTIIRA engages with policymakers and regulatory bodies to advocate for supportive policies and regulations that facilitate the adoption of new technologies. The organization also contributes to the development of industry standards and guidelines, ensuring the secure and efficient application of advanced water treatment solutions.

05

INNOVATION INITIATIVES ACROSS THE WATER VALUE CHAIN

- **Technology Transfer and Commercialization:** WTIIRA supports the transfer and commercialization of new technologies through its network of industry partners and investors. By bridging the gap between research and market deployment, WTIIRA helps introducing groundbreaking solutions that tackle essential water issues.
- **Public Awareness and Engagement:** Recognizing the importance of public awareness and engagement, WTIIRA conducts outreach and education campaigns to raise awareness about the benefits and importance of new water treatment technologies. These efforts aim to foster community support and acceptance of innovative solutions.

Water Transmission Innovation in KSA

WTIIRA has been providing a supportive role to WTTCO for water transmission innovation. WTIIRA is helping in modernizing water transmission systems in Saudi Arabia [12].

Key innovations and projects include:

- **Pipeline Upgrades:** WTIIRA has successfully carried out a study examining the impact of high chloride levels and total dissolved solids (TDS) on current transmission pipelines, and has provided recommended limits for water chemistry to ensure the safe operation of these existing systems.
- **Smart Water Grids:** WTIIRA is engaged in projects that integrate smart technologies into its water distribution systems. These advancements offer insights into flow rates, leak detection, and pipeline condition, facilitating predictive maintenance and guaranteeing continuous service.

- **Energy-Efficient Pumping Systems:** WTIIRA is implementing energy-efficient pumping stations that cut down on the total energy needed for water transport, thereby reducing operational expenses and lessening environmental impact.
- **Mega Transmission Projects:** WTIIRA has been engaged in multiple major water transmission initiatives designed to connect desalination facilities to regions experiencing water shortages. These initiatives consist of extensive pipeline systems that guarantee reliable water access in both urban and rural settings.
- **Support to WTTCO:** works in close partnership with WTTCO to ensure the efficient operation and upkeep of water transmission projects. This collaboration promotes the sharing of knowledge, exchange of technology, and development of skills to address the increasing water demands of the kingdom. Recently, WTIIRA has launched initiatives focused on leak detection and minimizing water loss by utilizing advanced technologies.

Water Distribution Innovation in KSA

WTIIRA plays a key role in supporting NWC in its mission to manage and improve water distribution across the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. WTIIRA's focus is on technological advancements, research, and the development of sustainable water distribution solutions to meet the growing demand for water in the Kingdom [12].

Below are some of the key ways in which WTIIRA supports NWC in water distribution:

- WTIIRA works closely with NWC to deploy smart water network technologies, which include real-time monitoring systems, internet of things (IOT) devices, and AI-driven analytics. These technologies help detect and repair leaks and optimize distribution, reducing water losses and improving overall system efficiency.
- The integration of digital twin technologies allows NWC to simulate water networks, predict potential failures, and perform. he initiatives collectively work toward creating a more sustainable and resilient water system, which is essential for the kingdom's development, particularly considering its water scarcity challenges.
- WTIIRA plays a crucial role in capacity building by training NWC's workforce in the latest water technologies and management strategies. This helps ensure that NWC staff are equipped with the necessary skills to operate, maintain, and optimize water distribution networks.
- WTIIRA fosters collaboration between NWC and academic institutions, enabling research programs that focus on water distribution challenges. Joint research projects help develop solutions tailored to Saudi Arabia's specific environmental and operational needs.
- WTIIRA has initiated several programs to support NWC via private sector participation in water distribution and infrastructure projects by facilitating public-private partnership (PPP). This partnership is vital for funding and implementing large-scale projects that require technological expertise and innovation.
- WTIIRA is assisting NWC to develop strategic water reserves, ensuring that sufficient water supplies are available during times of drought or emergency. This includes supporting the creation of underground storage facilities and developing systems for storing surplus desalinated water.

Wastewater Treatment & Reuse in KSA

SIO is committed to optimizing water use and enhancing the efficiency of irrigation practices in the Kingdom. Its program initiative focuses on promoting sustainable water management through advanced irrigation technologies, conserving water resources, and modernizing agricultural practices [12].

Here are the main initiatives highlighted:

- **Improving Economic Sustainability and Legislative Structure:** This initiative aims to improve the economic stability of the irrigation sector by reinforcing the legislative and institutional structures. It guarantees that regulations promote sustainable practices, encouraging long-term growth and efficiency in the management of water resources.
- **Upgrading Modern Irrigation Techniques:** SIO is committed to incorporating cutting-edge irrigation technologies. This initiative advocates for the implementation of modern, efficient irrigation systems and offers extension services to farmers and other stakeholders.
- **Strengthening Water Use Efficiency Standards:** A key focus here is to ensure adherence to water usage standards to boost efficiency. This includes monitoring and enforcing water conservation strategies, reducing waste, and aligning irrigation practices with sustainable water use.
- **Achieving Optimal Water Supply for Sustainability:** SIO aims to ensure an optimal and reliable water supply for irrigation by managing resources sustainably. This initiative supports the efficient allocation of water, ensuring that agricultural and other water-dependent activities have adequate supply while preserving resources for future use.

Saudi Arabia's water sector is poised to enter a new phase of transformative growth driven by technological innovation, strategic investment, and policy modernization. As the Kingdom advances toward Vision 2030, innovation must move consistently and systematically through the national water innovation funnel from Scouting and Research to Piloting and Technology Validation, Commercialization and Early Market Entry, and finally Scaling and Impact Assessment. The Saudi Water Authority (SWA) will play a central enabling role by coordinating research programs, incentivizing industrial participation, building strong international partnerships, and ensuring regulatory frameworks support rapid, responsible technology deployment.

In the Scouting and Research phase, the Kingdom should enhance integration between universities, research centres, industry, and utilities to generate a steady pipeline of high-value concepts. Establishing a national "Saudi Water Innovation Needs Map" will enable research to focus on priority themes including energy-efficient desalination, non-revenue water reduction, digital water analytics, and circular economy resource recovery. Institutionalizing competitive calls and thematic research clusters will further strengthen early-stage discovery and ensure solutions align closely with national strategic goals.

During the piloting and technology validation phase, Saudi Arabia has already demonstrated strong momentum through initiatives such as AI-based NRW reduction pilots at Ras Al-Khair and Zero-Liquid-Discharge (ZLD) trials at Haql [5].

To accelerate translation from concept to demonstration, the Kingdom should develop standardized living-lab testbeds across desalination, wastewater treatment, and distribution networks. Independent performance verification, such as global best-practice models adopted by Singapore's PUB and Denmark's water living labs, will reduce uncertainty, de-risk adoption, and strengthen investor confidence.

FUTURE OUTLOOK AND RECOMMENDATIONS

For commercialization and early market entry, dedicated financing and structured procurement mechanisms will be essential to convert validated solutions into scalable businesses. Saudi Arabia is already enabling market transition through renewable-powered desalination initiatives and fiscal incentives for sustainable technologies.

At the Scaling and Impact assessment stage, innovation deployment must be accompanied by rigorous performance monitoring and transparent reporting frameworks. Projects such as brine mineral recovery in Haql and planned lithium extraction facilities signal the Kingdom's ambition to lead in water-linked resource valorization. Establishing a centralized National Water Innovation Dashboard will ensure measurable accountability against key national sustainability targets, including energy consumption, recovery efficiency, brine salinity control, non-revenue water reduction, and plant operating uptime.

Looking forward, emerging technology themes will continue shaping the Kingdom's water future. Artificial intelligence and smart water platforms will enhance operational reliability and predict system behaviour; next-generation desalination membranes and ZLD systems will significantly reduce energy demand and environmental footprint; renewable integration will advance decarbonization across the water-energy nexus; and large-scale brine mining will unlock new economic value streams. To maintain global leadership, Saudi Arabia must continue strengthening R&D infrastructure, scaling pilot capabilities, and expanding industrial-academic partnerships—while reinforcing an innovation-friendly investment and regulatory ecosystem.

International evidence indicates that water-sector innovation is highly labour-intensive, generating between 10 and 15 total jobs for every USD 1 million invested, with significant spillovers across manufacturing, engineering and digital services. Based on these benchmarks, innovations in the water sector could create tens of thousands of direct and indirect jobs in the upcoming years [20] [21] [22].

In summary, Saudi Arabia has established a strong foundation for water sector transformation. Moving forward, a consistent focus on strategic alignment, accelerated piloting, market-readiness, and measurable sustainability outcomes will be essential. By embedding innovation into every stage of its water sector development model, the Kingdom is well-positioned to become a global benchmark for resilient, efficient, and future-ready water systems—delivering long-term economic, environmental, and societal value in line with Vision 2030.

07

CONCLUSIONS

This report highlights the essential role of innovation in Saudi Arabia's water sector and underlines the SWA's responsibility in driving progress that supports Vision 2030. By guiding Research, Piloting, Commercialization, and scaling activities, SWA is creating the conditions for a stronger and more sustainable water future. The integration of new technologies such as AI, renewable-powered desalination, and advanced brine recovery shows clear potential to improve efficiency and sustainability across the Kingdom. For example, AI systems tested at Ras Al-Khair reduced water losses by 15%, while solar-powered desalination in Al Khafji cut carbon emissions by 60,000 metric tons per year [5]. These kinds of innovations, if expanded, can help ensure water security, reduce costs, and contribute to economic diversification. At the same time, challenges remain. Saudi Arabia continues to expand wastewater reuse and reduce distribution network losses, although further progress is needed to align with high international standards. Advanced practices in reuse and efficiency are supported by strong regulatory frameworks and digital water management systems. Closing these gaps will require faster investment in reuse projects, stronger leakage management, and wider use of digital monitoring systems. Saudi Arabia already shows leadership in desalination and brine resource recovery, achieving high efficiency in energy use.

In summary, SWA has laid a strong foundation by establishing an Innovation Funnel that connects ideas to Pilots, Commercialization, and Scaling. The next step is to strengthen efficiency in the early stages of the funnel and ensure that scaled solutions deliver measurable results. By doing so, Saudi Arabia can not only secure its water future but also become a global example of sustainable and innovative water management.

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